

ISic3011

I.Sicily inscription 3011

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

dedication

Material

limestone

Object

altar

Editor

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

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Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Syracusae

Place of origin (modern)

Siracusa

Provenance

Nr. Theatre

Coordinates

Current Location

Italy, Sicily, Siracusa

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

Edition: PHI329738

1. Πυρ [— — — — —]

2. ΑΓ [— — — — —]

3.

Edition: PHI331243

1. σπέ[νδεται(?)]·

2. Πῦρ·

3. Ἄρκο.

4. ἔξο [υσίαι]

5. [— — κ]α [ι]

6. [Δε] ιφέλο⁻ (?) .

7.

Apparatus

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 645359

PHI 329738

PHI 331243

Bibliography

1923-. Supplementum epigraphicum graecum. *Supplementum epigraphicum graecum*. At 34.0977

1923-. Supplementum epigraphicum graecum. *Supplementum epigraphicum graecum*. At 15.0578

Neutsch, B. 1954. Archäologische Grabungen und Funde im Bereich der Soprintendenzen von Sizilien (1949-1954). *Archäologischer Anzeiger*. 69: 466-706. At 595-596 604-605

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